

MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF ENTOMOPATHOGENIC NEMATODES STEINERNEMA CARPOCAPSEA TYPE AND ITS EFFICACY IN CONTROL OF THE CUCURBIT FLY

Huda M. A.* , Khansaaa S. Farman* and Jawad B. Al-Zaidawi**

* Faculty of education for pure science, university of Diyala, Ministry of higher education, Iraq.

** Integrated Pest Management Center, Ministry of Science and Technology, Iraq.

E-mail: jawadbulbul500@gmail.com

Abstract

The current study aimed to detect the presence of Entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs) and isolate them from soils of some areas of Diyala Governorate, Iraq. The isolates were molecularly identified, and the results showed, depending on the symptoms of infection, the color of the infected large wax larvae, and some taxonomic morphological characteristics, that all isolates were of the genus Steinernema, and the molecular identification, compared to the isolates recorded in the global gene bank, showed that the isolates belong to the *S. carpocapsea* type. Nematodes were used experimentally to study their efficiency in controlling the cucurbit fruit fly insect, and the results of the pathogenicity study of the local and commercial *S. carpocapsea* species on cucurbit fruit fly larvae confirmed that the local isolation is very effective in causing death on the last stage larvae of cucurbit fruit fly under laboratory conditions. Three concentrations of 25, 50, and 100 larvae/IJS were used for each of the local and commercial isolates. The death rate after three days of experimental treatment with the local isolate for the last stage larvae of the cucurbit fruit fly reached 50, 66, 56, 33, and 83%, respectively. In commercial isolates, the death rates reached to 66.66, 86.66, and 96.66%, respectively, these were compared with the control treatment, and there were significant differences among the concentrations of each type. the LSD values for the local isolate was 8.74 and for the commercial 8.05, and significant differences appeared between the local and commercial types during each concentration, and the value of LSD for each of the concentrations 25, 50, 100 / 5.94, 7.06, 6.88 larvae /IJS, respectively, and the value of LC50 reached 31,454 larvae / IJS.

Keywords: Entomopathogenic nematodes, Steinernema carpocapsae, biological control, Dacus ciliates, molecular identification

Introduction

Many studies have been carried out around the world, which aim to investigate and detect the presence of entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNS), and certain types exist globally, some of which are found in cultivated and uncultivated lands, and some of them spread in specific areas. Isolation and identification of naturally spreading entomopathogenic nematodes (EPNs) has become the first essential step for laboratory propagation and use in biological control of various insect pests (Grewal and others, 2005), It was recorded for the first time in Iraq by isolating it from the long-horned palm stem borer and the palm stalk borer. The results proved its effectiveness in combating these insects in the laboratory, and the killing rate was 100%, except for the

pomegranate stem borer, which was not affected by them. It also achieved an efficiency in killing the infected palm borer larvae by 70% (Al-Jubouri and Saleh, 2001).

EPNs are considered one of the most important biological agents used effectively in the control of a wide range of economic insect pests for more than 130 years (Lacey and others, 2015), where they occupy the second most important biopesticide used against these pests after bacteria (Lewis and Clarke, 2012) have been resorted to as a result of the damage caused by chemical pesticides to humans and their environment and the emergence of insect strains resistant to these pesticides (Roditakis and others, 2015; 2003, Ehlers), which led to the need to find a safe alternative method.

The cucurbit fruit fly *Dacus ciliates* back to the family Tephritidae, and it is one of the main and important economic pests that cause economic damage to the crops of the Cucurbits family (Al-Dawood, 2013). The cucurbit fruit fly was first recorded in 1921 (Bezzi, 1924) Ethiopia is the original home of this insect and then moved to Sudan and then to Egypt (Maher, 1957). The first appearance of this economic insect in Iraq during the autumn season 1988 in the areas of Kut and Al-Amarah and its identification on the fruits of cucurbits (Moanas and Abdul-Rassoul, 1989) Al-Jubouri (1999) indicated that there was a loss in cucurbit crops for the years 1998 and 1999, which amounted to more than 50% of the crops and this increased the rate is up to 95% in some years, especially in the central and southern region of Iraq (Al-Waeli, 2014) and the cause of this damage is the feeding of the larvae on the fruits of these crops (2015, Delpoux and Deguine), as the females make a hole using the egg-laying machine to lay their eggs in it which leads to wrinkling and rotting of the fruits as a result of the growth of fungi and bacteria on them, causing their spoilage and low quality (Azab and Kara, 1953). The expansion of the cultivation of cucurbit fruits in Iraq, especially as they were grown twice a year, as well as the environmental conditions suitable for the insect's life and the lack of vital enemies for it. All these factors led to the invasion of these insects to the crops of the cucurbit family and the increase in their damage, and consequently led to the intensification of the farmers' suffering due to the severity of their infection with cucurbit fruits in most of the governorates of the country cause great economic damage as a result of the larvae dependence on fruits for their nutrition, which leads to rotting and poor quality and consequently the difficulty of marketing them (Mahdi, 2000).

Because of the economic losses, researchers tended to find a comprehensive and successful way to solve the problem of the cucurbit fruit fly insect, which has been exhausted by farmers in various regions of Iraq, as chemical pesticides were initially used mainly and because of their negative effects on the ecosystem, as it is considered one of the important means of pollution in the environment (Shaaban and Al-Malih, 1993) and its inability to control insects that spend some stages of their life inside the plant parts (Ahmed and Hugne, 1969), which forced them to search for alternative methods that are safe in terms of health and less harmful to the environment and avoid the emergence of resistant strains of pesticides (Al Taweel and others, 2005).

Materials and methods

1- Isolation of entomopathogenic nematodes

The experiments for the study were carried out during the years 2020-2021 on soil samples collected from 4 sites that included agricultural fields in the Khalis district, orchards and uncultivated lands in the Muqdadiya district and agricultural fields in Bani Saad district in Diyala governorate of Iraq.

To ascertain the presence or absence of entomopathogenic nematodes, the third stage larvae of the great wax moth were used as an insect trap described by Bedding & Akhurst (1975). In plastic containers with a volume of 250 cm³, five larvae were placed in each box in the middle to ensure that they spread in the sample, It was tightly covered and turned to ensure movement of the larvae into the soil. The third and fourth stage larvae of the great wax worm were used and kept at laboratory temperature (25 ± 5 °C) and they were monitored to search for dead larvae due to insect-pathogenic nematodes every two days for a week. The information on the plastic bag was recorded on the plastic insulation tray as well as the date of laying the larvae. When dead larvae are found, they are washed with sterile distilled water and transferred to dishes to isolate nematodes by the White trap technique (White, 1927).

2- Quantitative propagation of EPNS

For the purpose of quantitative propagation of EPNs and preparing them for pathogenicity experiment, sterile Petri dishes 9 cm in diameter and 2 cm in width will be prepared and Whatman No.1 filter papers are placed in each dish. Then, the nematode suspension stock or collected from infected larvae is added at a rate of 100 Ijs the third stage larve of (EPNs) / larva of the great wax worm at a rate of 10 dishes for each type of (EPNs) that were used in the pathogenesis experiment, which will include (local EPNs) and a type of (commercial EPNs) imported from outside Iraq.

3- Molecular identification

There are several steps implemented to complete the molecular identification process, which included:

- DNA extraction

For the purpose of DNA extraction, a special kit from one of the approved companies (Macrogen Corporation) was used. In this case, adults were isolated and used, with an average of one adult, for this purpose. The steps for extraction attached to the kit are followed in order to preserve the DNA genetic material at the end at a temperature of -20°C until it is used in the other stage, which is the PCR.

- PCR technique

For the purpose of carrying out the PCR, the ITS gene segment that was used in the molecular identification process was selected by using its primers which are TW81 (GTT TCC GTA GGT GAA CCT GC) and AB 28 (ATA TGC TTA AGT TCA GCG GGT) (Al-Zaidawi, 2019) and this was done by using 25 µl of content which includes 2.51 µl of Master mix and 1 µl of each Forward and Reverse Primer (2 Primer) and 6.5 µl of Denials water, 4 microliter of microliter of EPNs DNA.

For the purpose of obtaining the genetic sequence, the PCR product was sent to the Korean company Macrogen, and the genetic sequence was obtained, which was genetically analyzed through special programs, BioEdit and MEGA7, and the genetic tree that was used in the identification process was obtained.

4- Pathogenicity of EPNS against cucurbit fruit fly larvae

The aqueous suspension containing EPNs was calculated to measure the average lethal concentration LC₅₀ for the isolates whose pathogenicity was tested according to (Lacey, 2012) equation as follows:

$$C1*V1=C2*V2$$

Whereas:

C1: nematode concentration in the main aqueous suspension (stock)

V2: The total volume of the main aqueous suspension (stock)

C2 : nematode concentration in 1 μ 10

V2: The volume of the aqueous suspension taken from the main suspension (10μl).

The average number of infective larvae of nematodes per 10 μl was calculated using the anatomical microscope at a rate of 10 times, and then the rate of infective juveniles per each drop (10μl) was counted.

Five concentrations of commercial and local nematodes were used to measure their pathogenicity and included the following concentrations: 25, 50, 100, 200, 300 IJs/insect.

Petri dishes were used for this purpose with an average of 3 dishes for each concentration (treatment) and each dish contained 10 *Dacus ciliates* larvae. Then the dishes were left under laboratory conditions and the results were recorded after 72 hours of treatment and the pathogenicity of the (EPNs) was measured by measuring the killing rate as well as the average killing LC₅₀ using Polo plus-probit and Logit analysis 0.1 program.

Results and discussion

The results of the molecular identification of the ITS gene segment of the isolated entomopathogenic individuals that cause the death of the largest wax larvae and the results of the electrophoresis (Fig. 1) showed that the chain length is 769 pb, the sequence of the nitrogenous bases shown in figure 4-3 and the genetic tree of the isolate under the symbol IRQ.DL.1 as well as matching with Some species of the genus *Stenernema* by comparison in the Genetic Information Center (NCBI) and compared with isolates and species recorded at the site through the use of the BLAST. Then the genetic tree was drawn under a comparison score (bootstrap) 1100 that the species belongs to *steinernema carpocapsae* compared to the species at 100% and that the total rate of disparity (the over aaverage) between the local isolate and the isolates that were compared with it on the international site of genetic information was 0.20, as shown in Genetic tree (Fig. 2) and Table (1)

Figure 1. Electrophoresis of the polymerase reaction product for the detection of the ITS gene on a (1%) agarose gel at a voltage of 120 V for 50 minutes, M: Marker (LDR) 100-1000 bp, 1-5: The number of samples for the PCR product containing the genetic material of local nematodes, CO-: PCR product that does not contain the genetic material (for comparison), CO+: commercial PCR product (for comparison)

Figure 2. Genetic tree showing the genetic relationship between the local isolate *S. carpocapsae* IRQ.DL.1 with 17 global isolates belonging to the genus *Steinernema* depending on the ITS genetic segment.

Table (1): Pairwise comparison of the number of different nucleotides between the local isolate of *S. carpocapsae* and the rest of the global isolates of the genus *Steinernema* depending on the ITS genetic segment

Steinernema species and outgroup species	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
IRQ_DL.1													
GQ421606 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> isolate Bcn14	0.00												
GQ421604 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> isolate Breton	0.00	0.01											
KC571265 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> isolate IS34	0.00	0.01	0.00										
GU395621 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> isolate A24	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00									
EU200353 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> isolate Badr-1	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01								
AY170334 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> strain SGIB	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01							
KC621916 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> isolate MDUST1	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01						
KJ818295 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> isolate DOK_83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00					
LN624759 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> isolate SG24	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00				
KJ950291 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> strain NCR	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00			
HQ190044 <i>Steinernema nepalense</i> voucher UGDM_1	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06		
AF121050 <i>Steinernema feltiae</i>	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.36	0.35	0.36	0.34	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.37	
EU200355 <i>Steinernema feltiae</i> isolate Malka	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.35	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.36	0.00
GU130182 <i>Steinernema</i> sp. T51	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.01	0.37
AF331915 <i>Steinernema scapterisci</i>	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.14	0.39
AY230164 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> strain All	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.35
GU395621 <i>Steinernema carpocapsae</i> isolate A241	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.36
KJ636408 <i>Heterorhabditis bacteriophora</i> HeRhBac5	1.01	1.02	1.01	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.02	1.00	1.01	1.02	1.02	1.06	1.14

4-2-2-3 Pathogenicity of EPNS against Cucurbit fruit fly larvae

The results of the laboratory experiment to measure the potency of nematodes showed a high sensitivity of the last stage of *Dacus ciliatus* larvae, specifically to the local and commercial isolates of *Steinernema carpocapsae* and to the different concentrations used against it in the experiment. *carpocapsae* is effective in killing these larvae after three days of treatment, as the killing rate at the concentration of nematodes/larva was 50, 66.6% for both local and commercial respectively, and this killing rate was higher with the concentration used when treatment was 50 nematodes/larva, which reached Killing rate 56.66 and 86.66 % for both local and commercial, respectively. The highest killing rate was at the highest concentration that was used at the equation 100 nematodes/larva. The killing rate reached 83,33, 96.66% for both local and commercial, respectively, compared to the control treatment (water only), and the results of the statistical analysis showed that there are differences as the nematodes isolated from the local environment and referred to in the study are linked in similar ways with this species was significant between the two local and commercial species during the same concentration at a significant level of 0.05, where the value of (LSD) for concentrations reached 25, 50, 100 nematodes/larva, having 5.94, 7.06, 6.88 , respectively, as well as significant differences between the concentrations of both local and commercial species in a language value (LSD) 8.74 and 8.05, respectively, at the same level of significance (Table 2) and Figure (3).

Table 2: Death rate of Laboratory Biological Experiment for the two species local and commercial *Steinernema carpocapsae* against *Dacus ciliatus* larvae

The studied sample	Concentrations				LSD
	%0	%25	50 %	%100	
Local <i>steinernema carpocapsae</i>	6.6	50	56.66	83.33	8.74 *
Commercial <i>steinernema carpocapsae</i>	6.0	66.66	86.66	96.66	8.05 *
LSD	1.52 NS	5.94 *	7.06 *	6.88 *	---

(.) $P \leq 0.05$ *

*Significant, NS insignificant

Figure 3. Pathogenic susceptibility of nematodes to local isolate compared to commercial isolate of *S. carpocapsae* under laboratory conditions on *Dacus ciliates* larvae, the different letters show significant differences between treatments at a significant level ($p < 0.05$).

Studies have shown that EPNs have the ability to infect a wide range of insect hosts and reproduce within them, but the type of EPNs or even the strain has a large role in the events of infection and their ideal reproduction (Georgis and others, 2006). The reason for testing the most virulent type in the control of the target pest is closely related to its penetration the pest evades its immune system through the ferocity of its companion bacterium (*Xenorhabdus nematophila*) (minas and others, 2016). (Rohde and others, 2012) mentioned that the relationship of (EPNs) - host is constrained by many factors, which makes it difficult to explain the association of a type

of (EPNs) with a specific host through one experiment, but it depends on the ability of the (EPN) type to penetrate the host, the incidence of infection, its location and reproduction in it.

The concentrations of the infective stage used in the control of types of fruit flies (Tephritid) vary according to the type of (EPNs) and the environmental factors surrounding the experiment and the type of pest to be controlled (Langford and others, 2014). In the larvae of the last stage of the *Dacus ciliatus*, the highest death rate was 83.33 and 96.66 at the highest concentration of 100 larvae, and the large natural openings of the body of fruit fly larvae and the lack of hardening of their body tissues were factors that led to a high death rate (Rohde and others, 2012) with a killing rate of 70% at concentration 100 Larvae three days after treatment to combat excess *Bactrocera dorsalis* oriental fruit (Aatif and others, 2019) This ratio is close to the killing rate in this study, which indicates that the larvae of the cucurbit fruit fly *S.carpocapsea* are sensitive to a degree similar to the sense of the oriental fruit fly, *S. carpocapsea* is considered effective in controlling insect pests. In the results of the Magnerian experiment of Darwish and others (2020) the death rate of larvae of young tomato leaves *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) treated with isolate RsT of the type *S.carpocapsea* between 21.8-90%, as well as confirmed by Ayukf and others, 2022 Local deer virulence of *H.bacteriophora* (GA1/ MK474645.1, SR/ M474617.1, MG2/ MK474643.1).

Isolate GA outperformed the two isolates SA1, MG2 with a death rate of 69.19% for third-stage larvae of the Mediterranean fruit fly. Through the results of the current and previous study, ERNs and *carpocapsea* are effective in controlling many local insect pests, especially cucurbit fruit fly larvae, which can be incorporated in the future in integrated management. For insects LC50 of the local *S.arpocapcea* isolate used in the study, the results indicate that the concentration needed to kill half of the insects, the cucurbit fruit fly used in the experiment, LC50 was 31,454 larvae of *S.arpocapcea*, and this converges with the results published by AL.Zaidawi and others, 2021, who studied the effect of three isolates *H. bacteriophora* and *S.arpocapsea* the commercial local of (*Microcerotermes diversus*) subterranean termite, and the value of LC50 *S.carpocapsea* in each of the dishes and the container containing sawdust was 15.9 termite /IJs (Al-zaidawi and others, 2021).

The LC50 in a petri-dish study using the RsT isolate of *S.carpocapsea* on the tomato leaf borer (*Tuta absoluta*) was 7.8 and the LC50 required to kill 50% of the community for *sopodoptera Litura* (fabricius) larvae treated with *H. indica* was 7.13±1. The LC50 value of three isolates of the type *H. bacteriophora* against larvae of the Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* wiedemann in soil 88 cm/ IJs (Iokov and others, 2022) reached 100%.

Conclusion

The (EPNs) isolated from the local environment have the ability to cause infestation and kill larvae of the cucurbit fruit fly even at low concentrations. In addition to this, It can be adopted as a local biological control agent as a successful alternative to chemical control.

Reference list

- Aatif, H., M., Hanif, M., Sh., Ferhan, M., Raheel, M., Shakeel, Q., Ashraf, W., Irfan Ullah, M. and Ali, S. (2019), Assessment of the entomopathogenic nematodes against maggots and pupae of the oriental fruit fly, *Bactrocera dorsalis* (Hendel) (Diptera: Tephritidae), under laboratory conditions, Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control, 29 (51).
- Abo Kaf, N., M. Al-Body, M. Mofleh and Gh. Zeini. (2022), Assessment of *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* (Rhabditida: Heterorhabditidae) Against *Ceratitis capitata* Wiedemann. Arab Journal of Plant Protection, 40(1): 48-56.
- Ibrahim J. AL-Jboory and Seba J. Saleh. (2001), New Record of Entomogenous Nematodes Isolated From Date Palm Stem Borers In Iraq, Basra Date Palm Research, 1 (1), 1-5.
- Al-Taweel, A., AL-Shammery, A. J., and Ahmed R., F. (2005), The effect of Gama ray on some biological factors of *Dacus ciliatus* Loew.(Diptera: Tephritidae), Agricultural Science Journal, 32(3).
- Al-waily, S. D., Abdul Qadar, A.. A. and Majde, A. K (2014), Influence of Biological and Chemical Factors in big cucumber fly *Dacus lonigistylus*(wideman) (Tephritidae :Diptera)on melons plant in some Areas of the province of Basrah, Dhiqar Sciences journal, 4(2),37-44.
- Al-Zaidawi, J. B., J. Karimi, and E. M. Moghadam.(2019). Molecular characterizations of the entomopathogenic nematodes, *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* and *Oscheius myriophilus* from Iraq. Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control, 29 (38).
- Al-Zaidawi, J. B., J. Karimi, and E. M. Moghadam. (2020) Entomopathogenic Nematodes as Potential Biological Control Agents of Subterranean Termite, *Microcerotermes diversus* (Blattodea: Termitidae) in Iraq, Environmental Entomology, 23(41), 1-10.
- Azab, A. K. and M. T. Kira (1954). The cucurbit fly, *Dacus ciliatus* (Loew) in Egyptian Society. Foad 1st in Bulletin of Entomology, 30: 379-382.
- Aldawood, A., S. (2013). Comparative study of Cucurbit fly: *Dacus ciliatus* Loew (Diptera: Tephritidae) infestation on Zucchini squash (*Cucurbita pepo* L.) at Huraimila and Diraab, Riyadh Region, Saudi Arabia, Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences, 6(2): 91 – 96.
- Bezzi, M. (1924). Notes on the Ethiopian Fruit-flies of the Family Trypa-neidae, other than *Dacus* (s.l.), with Descriptions of New Genera and Species (Dipt.).-I, [Bulletin of Entomological Research](#), 8(3-4): 215-251.
- Bedding, R.A. and Akhurst, R.J. (1975) A simple technique for the detection o f insect paristic rhabditid nematodes in soil, *Nematologica*, 21(1).**
- Delpoux, C. and [Deguine](#), J.,Ph. (2015). Implementing a Spinosad-Based Local Bait Station to Control *Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Diptera: Tephritidae) in High Rainfall Areas of Reunion Island, [Journal Insect Society](#). 15(1): 11.
- Darwish, A., A. Bashir and K. El-Asas. 2020. Effectiveness of some local isolates of entomopathogenic nematodes for the control of *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) under laboratory and field conditions. Arab Journal of Plant Protection, 38(4): 318-326.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Ehlers, R.U. (2003). Biocontrol nematodes. in Hokkanen, H.M.T. and Hajek, A. E. (eds) Environmental Impacts of Microbial Insecticides, need and method for risk management. Kluwer academic publishers, Dordrecht, The Netherlands, pp. 177-220.

Georgis, R., Koppenhöfer, A., M., Lacey, A., A., Bélair, G., Duncan, L., W., Grewal, P., S. Samish, M., Tan, L., Torr, P. and Van, W. H. (2006). Successes and failures in the use of parasitic nematodes for pest control, *Biological control*, 38(1): 103-123.

[Grewal](#), P., S., Ehlers, R., U. and [Shapiro-Ilan](#), D., I. (2005). Critical issues and research needs for expanding the use of nematodes in biological control in *Nematodes as biological control agents*, CABI, New York, 479-490.

Huque, H., Ahmed, C.R. (1969). Studies on the control of *Dacus ciliatus* Loew (Tephritidae, Diptera) by sterile-male release technique, *International Journal Applied Radiation and Isotopes*, 20: 791-795.

Lacey, L.A., Grzywacz, D., Shapiro-Ilan, D.I., Frutos, R., Brownbridge, M. and Goettel M.S. (2015). Insect pathogens as biological control agents: Back to the future, *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*, 1: 132-141.

Langford, E. A., Nielsen, U. N., Johnson, S. N., & Riegler, M. (2014). Susceptibility of Queensland fruit fly, *Bactrocera tryoni* (Froggatt) (Diptera: Tephritidae), to entomopathogenic nematodes. *Biological Control*, 69, 34-39.

Lewis, E., E. and Clarke, D. (2012). Nematode Parasites and Entomopathogens in Vega, F. and Kaya, H., K. *Insect Pathology*, 2nd ed, pp. 295-424.

Maher, A. (1957). On the bionomics of *Dacus ciliatus*, Loew (Diptera: Tephritidae). *Bulletin of Society of Entomology, Egypt*. 41: 527-533.

Moans, A.M.H. and M.S. Abdul-Rassoul (1989). First record of *Dacus ciliatus* (Loew) (Diptera: Tephritidae) as a pest of cucumber in Iraq. *Bulletin of the Iraq Natural History Museum*, 8(2): 173-174.

Mahdee, H., S., A. (2000). Environmental and biological study of *Dacus ciliatus*, Loew (Diptera: Tephritidae) and evaluation some its control methods, thesis, University of Baghdad, Faculty of Agriculture, Iraq. P. 102.

Roditakis, E; Vasakis, E; Grispou, M; Stavrakaki, M; Nauen, R; Gravouil, M; Bassi, A. (2015). First report of *Tuta absoluta* resistance to diamide insecticides, *Journal of Pest Science*, 88(1): 9-16.

Rohde C, Moino AJ, Carvalho FD, Silva MAT (2012) Selection of entomopathogenic nematodes for the control of the fruit fly *Ceratitidis capitata* (Diptera: Tephritidae). *Revista Brasileira de Ciencias Agrarias*, 7: 797-802.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Shaban, A and Al-Mallah, N., M. (1993). Pesticides, Book House of Printing and publishing, Ministry of higher education and scientific research, Al-Musal University, Iraq, P. 520.

White, G. (1927). A method for obtaining infective nematode larvae from cultures. Science (Washington) 66: 302–303.

ELSEVIER
Scopus

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7249109
Journal of East China University of Science and Technology
Volume 65, Issue 3, 2022 (ISSN: 1006-3080)